

Helix Nebula – The Science Cloud

Deliverable Title: D5.2 Summary report of the pilot stage: lessons learned

Partner Responsible: INFN

Work Package: WP5

Submission Due Date: 30.06.2018

Actual Submission Date: 09.08.2018

Distribution: Public

Nature: Report

Abstract: This report presents how the first part of the pilot phase of the HNSciCloud Pre-Commercial Procurement project was organised and suggests a number of lessons that were learned during this period that may be useful in the continuation of the phase.

Document Information Summary

Deliverable number:	D5.2
Deliverable title:	Summary report of the pilot stage: lessons learned
Editor:	Andrea Chierici
Contributing Authors:	Bob Jones, Joao Fernandes
Reviewer(s):	WP5 members
Work package no.:	WP5
Work package title:	Pilot Platform
Work package leader:	INFN
Work package participants:	CERN, CNRS, EMBL/EBI, ESRF, DESY, INFN, KIT, IFAE, SURFSara
Distribution:	Public
Nature:	Report
Version/Revision:	1.0
Draft/Final:	Final
Keywords:	HNSciCloud, pilot platform

Disclaimer

Helix Nebula – The Science Cloud (HNSciCloud) with Grant Agreement number 687614 is a Pre-Commercial Procurement Action funded by the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020.

This document contains information on the HNSciCloud core activities, findings and outcomes and it may also contain contributions from distinguished experts who contribute to HNSciCloud. Any reference to content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organisation and publication date. This document has been produced with co-funding from the European Commission. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the HNSciCloud consortium and cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission.

Grant Agreement Number: 687614

Start Date: 01 January 2018

Duration: 36 Months

Log Table

Issue	Date	Description	Author/Partner
V0.1	25/05/2018	Initial Draft	Andrea Chierici/INFN
V0.2	5/7/2018	Added executive summary	Andrea Chierici
V0.3	18/7/2018	Added conclusions	Andrea Chierici
V0.4	25/7/2018	Additional lessons learned added	Bob Jones
V0.5	31/7/2018	Review	Andrea Chierici
V0.6	05/08/2018	Executive summary	Bob Jones
V1.0	06/08/2018	Final Version	

Executive Summary

This report presents the lesson learned on the first part of the Pilot Phase of the HNSciCloud project.

During this five-month period, the contractors (RHEA and T-Systems) were requested to expand prototypes implemented during the previous phase to become stable and resourceful pilot platforms. These pilot platforms should be stable enough to allow procurers' users to use them for their scientific computing needs.

Extended testing addressing functionality, interoperability, security, robustness and scalability was performed by the buyers groups' IT specialists in order to assess the pilots.

Two progress reviews assessed the pilot platforms and written feedback was provided to the contractors. Overall, the pilot platforms proposed by the contractors to meet the PCP challenges have been developed, successfully deployed, scaled-up and are accessible to the buyers group while the solutions for transparent data access are not yet ready for large-scale deployment.

The lessons learned during the execution of the first phase of the HNSciCloud pilot platform deployments are as follows:

- Formal progress reviews, scheduled during the execution phase of the PCP, provide decision points that ensure the results of the project are relevant for procurers.
- Reorientation of solutions are simpler to implement during the transition between phases that within a phase of execution.
- A service conformance test-suite that can be executed by contractors without external support simplifies the development and deployment process.
- A market readiness assessment is necessary to ensure all the support activities to bring a service to market are in place.
- A service providers' self-assessment of the Technology Readiness Level is not sufficient and some external assessment is required for widespread production usage.
- For large-scale production usage, data flows need to be understood in advance to establish the full network connectivity requirements.
- A common approach for a proxy service and group/role/authZ attribute management mapping should be foreseen in the context of EduGAIN.
- Cloud service migration and exit strategies are essential and should be addressed in the cloud service agreement.
- An agreed mechanism for identifying and recording service outages is necessary.
- Open source interface packages, such as Terraform and Libcloud, simplify the porting of applications between cloud services and reduce the reliance cloud technical brokers.
- Exchanges of resource quotas facilitate scalability testing and increase added-value for procurers.

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1. Introduction

The pilot phase of the HNSciCloud PCP is the final step in the implementation of the hybrid cloud platform proposed by the contractors that were selected in the call-off that took place after the prototype phase. During the period January to June 2018, the technical activities of the project were organised by Work Package 5 (WP5) and led by INFN. By the end of WP5, each contractor produced a set of deliverables specified in the tender that focused on scalability of the platforms and on training of new users that will access the pilot at the end of this phase.

WP5 was responsible for guiding the contractors throughout the first part of the pilot phase, testing the scalability of the proposed platforms, organizing the procurers' hosted events and assessing the deliverables produced by the contractors. WP5 is composed of members of the following organisations belonging to the buyers group: CERN, CNRS, DESY, EMBL-EBI, ESRF, IFAE, INFN, KIT, STFC and SURFsara.

This first part of the pilot phase lasted for five months, from January to May 2018, starting with a face-to-face kick-off meeting hosted by INFN, followed by one mid-term review at month two, two procurers' hosted events (ESRF and CERN), and finished with the face-to-face end of WP5 review.

This document contains the lessons learned during the first part of the pilot phase based on the feedback received from the buyers' group and the contractors.

2. Execution of the first part of the pilot phase

The figure below shows the timeline of the execution of the pilot phase, including deliverables, milestones and IaaS capacity for the pilot provided by each contractor in terms of cores and storage capacity. WP5 activity ended with the second progress review, M-PIL-3.2.

APPENDIX 3: TIME SCHEDULE PHASE 3

Phase 3: Pilot Platform

01/2/2018 till 30/11/2018

3. Lessons learned about the first part of the pilot phase

This section describes different aspects of the execution of the first part of the pilot phase and identifies a number of lesson learned.

3.1. Research and development process

The first part of the pilot phase produced good results in terms of resource utilization and reached the main objective of opening of the platform to general users. However, most of the issues identified during the prototype phase were not yet resolved at the start of the pilot phase. This mainly concerned solutions addressing the transparent data access PCP challenge, which required significant testing effort by the buyers group resulting in only partial improvements to date. Alternative implementations were discussed but, at this stage of the project, it was too late for any solution change that would require significant deployment and testing effort. The buyers group decided to give the contractors the test suites and ask them to identify testers within their consortium to perform quality assurance tests on each new version of the software. If the same approach had been used in the prototyping phase then it could have reduced the total testing effort.

The buyers' group, mainly due to brokering issues, did not identify significant advantages with the multi-cloud approach proposed by one of the contractors. Therefore, the contractor was asked to reorient their proposal to a single cloud solution. This flexibility demonstrated by the contractor resulted in a cloud solution that has proved very effective for the procurers with a few but meaningful differences compared to the multi-cloud solution.

Had the testing activities been fully completed by the end of the prototype phase, as initially planned, then this reorientation of a solution could have been included in the pilot phase call-off rather than as a outcome of a pilot phase progress review. This would have simplified the execution of the pilot phase with less impact for the contractor's consortium and ensured continuous access to the platform for the buyers group. This experience also highlights the importance of organizing progress reviews with the execution phase that act as decision points for the project.

During this phase, procurers shared quota in order to enable scalability tests and to keep resource usage at a high level. The target was achieved for CPU resource utilization, while for storage, mainly due to transparent data access issues already discussed, the utilization remained low. Related to this issue is the request of some procurers for the contractors to compensate them when cloud resources could not be consumed due to service limitations.

A mechanism for identifying and recording service outages is necessary. With all contractors there were service outages during the pilot phase, some scheduled and some unforeseen, which interrupted the activities. Service outages need to be measured against the service level agreement (SLA) and, if the SLA is breached, compensation (in terms of service credits or vouchers) made by the contractor to the procurers. This general principle was agreed with the contractors but the mechanism to systematically identify and record such outages was not specified and led to some contention between the parties.

As the R&D activities come to the pilot phase then support functions, such as a ticketing system and a single point for documentation become more important, especially when deadline with end-users. Buyers' group thinks that for future projects, these points have to be raised at a high important level, because they can significantly simplify the communication and the dissemination of information among the users.

Taking into account the points raised above, it is clear that the pilot phase has seen some very intense interaction between the public procurers and both commercial and public service providers. Differences have been apparent in the approach to service support across commercial and public sector providers in the context of HNSciCloud. The commercial providers approach is part of their 'go to market' process to support their commercialisation plan while the public service providers continued to follow a prototyping approach which made it more difficult to engage end-users who were not familiar with the project's history. The use of a test-suite has helped to focus the expected level of service required by the procurers and has occasionally exposed differences with respect to the service providers' appreciation of their service readiness, notably for public sector service providers. In particular, the lack of testing of some of the services by the contractors before making them available to the Buyers Group has caused frustration and delays for WP5. The situation could have been improved if the Buyers Group test-suite could be executed stand-alone without the Buyers' intervention. As an intermediate measure, it was agreed that the service providers concerned must run their own benchmarking tests on the Buyers Group installations before announcing software releases are ready for use. This suggests that a service providers' self-assessment of the Technology Readiness Level¹ is not sufficient and some external assessment will be required for widespread production usage. A similar situation exists for the assessment of IT service management where FitSM² is promoted amongst public sector service providers as a free and lightweight standards family aimed at facilitating service management in IT service provision, including federated

¹ TRL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level#European_Commission_definition

² <https://www.itemo.org/fitsm/>

scenarios. While some of the service providers in HNSciCloud have experience with FitSM³ it was not consistently applied during the pilot phase.

In addition, a market readiness assessment⁴ is necessary to ensure all the support activities to bring a service to market are in place. Exposing the pilot phase services to end-users and site administrators in order to collect their feedback will provide one form of external assessment but at the risk of alienation if the services do not match their needs. Consequently, it is important to carefully select the end-users and site administrators taking into account their profiles and expectations. The project is investing significant effort to ensure such feedback is gathered via a series of events scheduled during the pilot phase.

To allow sites willing to test scalability performance of the pilots to scale beyond the allotted amount of resources, we implemented a quota share mechanism, managed manually each week. This approach was successful for pilot phase but because it was managed through emails, it required regular intervention and was error prone. In addition, interaction with contractors occurred mainly via emails, instead of through ticketing systems, due to some platform limitations and this should not be the communication mechanism at this stage of the project.

3.2. High performance I/O applications require dedicate network connectivity

Network connectivity and performance issues have continued to be a source of delay in the pilot phase. Even with good working relationships between procuring research organisations, GEANT, NRENs and the cloud service providers, it has been difficult to ensure reliable end-to-end networking performance which is a cornerstone of the hybrid cloud model. For future large-scale production usage, data flows need to be understood in advance to establish the full network connectivity requirements. In case of applications with significant I/O requirements, we would recommend dedicated network circuits connecting cloud providers and the procuring research organisations.

This approach has been taken for connecting CERN's on-site data centre with the Wigner data centre in Hungary using 3x100Gbps links provided by GEANT and T-Systems. For a collection of procuring research organisations and multiple commercial cloud service

³ https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/10.1007%2F978-3-319-10894-0_7.pdf

⁴ For an example of market readiness assessment for H2020 project results please refer to "From Project To Product: A New & Improved Approach to Technology & Market Readiness" produced by the CloudWatch2 project, April 2017,

http://www.cloudwatchhub.eu/sites/default/files/CloudWATCH_From_Project_To_Product.pdf

providers (as is envisaged for the EOSC), a model similar to that established for the WLCG, based on LHCOPN⁵ and LHCONE⁶ could be more appropriate.

An alternative to dedicated circuits that can be substantially cheaper is IP filtering across the GEANT Cloud VRF (Virtual Routing and Forwarding) between source and destination locations, specifically research organisations and cloud providers or vice-versa. This setup assumes that bandwidth capacity through the VRF is essentially limited by the network switch port capacity to which the cloud provider is connected, when peering to the GEANT VRF network.

This option still remains to be tested in order to understand the overall reliability and peak bandwidth capacity that can be reached using a traffic filtering configuration.

In addition, the need for direct data flow between commercial cloud providers over the GEANT network has to be well understood in advance since it has an impact on networking policy. Monitoring of data movement and tagging capabilities by the cloud provider are possible techniques to be demonstrated in order to ensure that the traffic is only R&E related.

Sometimes it happened that we needed to ask for a special tuning of the network and the interaction with the people involved resulted being very slow. There are many actors involved in the process: procurers, OTC/Exoscale, DFN, GEANT with unknown dependencies. For future activities, we should agree (beforehand) on methods and responsibilities to address network issues.

3.3. Federated Identity Management

The contractors involved in HNSciCloud have taken different directions concerning the implementation of federated identity management, specifically concerning the use of a proxy service.

While eduGAIN inter-federation framework does provide a base for creating a federated identity environment, additional agreements and specifications are needed so service providers can determine which identity attributes are to be considered and matched in order to provide access and authorisation to resources. ELIXIR has formalised such agreements and specifications in the context of the life sciences community and this simplified the deployment. Adding a proxy service, such as Keycloak, can enable attribute matching and translation across different federated authentication sources and protocols. However, concerns have been raised that such a service would not simplify the attribute management but instead would introduce another layer of complexity.

⁵ <http://lhcopn.web.cern.ch/lhcopn/>

⁶ <http://lhcone.web.cern.ch/>

In this regard, T-Systems has evaluated a potential implementation of a Keycloak service. Concisely, the conclusions of the provider are that a proxy service (in this case based on Keycloak), would not simplify the rule conversion management currently implemented on their solution in order to assign and enforce permissions and authorisation to access compute/storage resources allocated to tenants at the cloud provision level. In addition, that approach introduces an additional layer of system management. The key issue for T-Systems in their understanding, is that it's quite difficult to conclude from most of the eduGAIN providers which (if any) of the attributes can be used to link users to groups and/or roles. The claim is that in this regard, ELIXIR manages this aspect in a better way than eduGAIN. T-Systems concluded that without the presence of this additional system management layer (proxy) there is a lower security risk of identities and tokens being misused or compromised since they are managed at one level only, the cloud provision level, in their particular case. Therefore, T-Systems proposes to continue with the functionality proposed and tested during the Prototype Phase and will further improve the documentation and training guides for the deployed Pilot, to ensure wide-spread use and acceptance of the functionality available.

RHEA, as part of its multi-cloud approach proposed for HNSciCloud, maintains a solution based on their own Keycloak service in order to address the challenge of Federated identity management in this context.

There are several recommendations to take away from this exercise:

- The AAI service delivery model should be defined during, if not before, the procurement phase
- For similar use cases (services procured for multiple international research communities), a platform (typically an IdP/SP service + group management) should be made available to support connection to eduGAIN
- Effort to deploy the AAI platform must be foreseen.

In the future, a common approach for a proxy service and group/role/authZ attribute management mapping should be foreseen in the context of EduGAIN. Ideally, a common service should be made available to all cloud service providers and procurers.

The experience gathered by the HNSciCloud project during its development and deployment of federated identity management in a hybrid cloud model for the research community has

been documented by the AARC2 project⁷ as a use-case and taken into account in the recently published report by the FIM4R group⁸.

3.4. Service migration and exit strategies

During the transition from the prototype to the pilot phase and following the re-positioning of the RHEA pilot platform, migration of user data and configuration information has been necessary. These migration tasks require cooperation between the users, procurers and cloud service providers.

The need for data repatriation at the end of the pilot phase has also limited the interest of user groups to deploy storage intensive use-cases. A longer-term engagement for access to the storage, together with a data back-up service, would probably increase the interest of such user groups to make more use of the storage capacity.

The contractual relationship should foresee access to the services as part of the termination process of the contract so users can re-patriate their data and configuration information. This will be an important requirement on all service providers, private or public, in the future EOSC.

The experience gathered by the HNSciCloud project is contributing to policy for the digital single market through participation of a project representative in the recently formed working group on cloud switching/porting data (SWIPO). The SWIPO working group will work on developing self-regulatory codes of conduct at Union level, as defined in the Commission's proposal on the free flow of non-personal data (COM(2017)495, article 6). Such codes of conduct should define best practices and information requirements to facilitate the switching of cloud service providers and to ensure that these providers supply professional users with sufficiently detailed, clear and transparent information before a contract for data storage and processing is concluded. The objective of SWIPO is to reduce the risk of 'vendor lock-in', as it will be easier to switch providers when it is clear which processes, technical requirements, timeframes and charges apply in case a professional user wants to switch to another provider or port data back to its own IT systems.

⁷ AARC2: Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration, <https://aarc-project.eu>

⁸ Federated Identity Management for Research Collaborations, Version: 2.0. Date: 9 July 2018, doi: [10.5281/zenodo.1296031](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1296031)

3.5. Cloud service brokers

While the procurers involved in HNSciCloud see value in having access to multiple, competing IaaS providers, the added technical value of a broker proved lower than expected. The procurers were able to port their tests and applications across multiple IaaS providers with acceptable levels of effort by making use of open source interface packages such as Terraform⁹ and Libcloud¹⁰.

Some of the procurers have their own equivalent of a broker managing multiple environments and an additional third-party broker did not bring significant added value. For example, some procurers provide job submission systems to their end-users and make use of batch systems that overlap with the functionality of a broker.

A broker may prove more valuable for other user groups and workload types. For example, end-users that interact directly with the services and are not executing high-throughput style workloads.

3.6. Resource quotas

Each procurer was allocated a quota of IaaS resources corresponding to their contribution to the total procurement budget. The procurers agreed to temporarily transfer, on a voluntary basis, IaaS resource capacity between their testing groups. This made it possible for the procurers testing groups to perform larger-scale tests than would have been possible using their own quotas. The results of such tests were shared with the cloud providers and all the procurers who were able to profit from the knowledge and experience gained.

Adjustments between the procurers were agreed on a weekly basis and implemented by the cloud providers.

4. Summary

This section summarises the lessons learned during the execution of the first phase of the HNSciCloud pilot platform deployments:

⁹ <https://www.terraform.io/>

¹⁰ <https://libcloud.apache.org/>

- Formal progress reviews, scheduled during the execution phase of the PCP, provide decision points that ensure the results of the project are relevant for procurers.
- Reorientation of solutions are simpler to implement during the transition between phases that within a phase of execution.
- A service conformance test-suite that can be executed by contractors without external support simplifies the development and deployment process.
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- A common approach for a proxy service and group/role/authZ attribute management mapping should be foreseen in the context of EduGAIN.
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- An agreed mechanism for identifying and recording service outages is necessary.
- Open source interface packages, such as Terraform and Libcloud, simplify the porting of applications between cloud services and reduce the reliance on cloud technical brokers.
- Exchanges of resource quotas facilitate scalability testing and increase added-value for procurers.